

MIMO MOBILE-to-MOBILE 5G COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS ALONG ELLIPTICAL GEOMETRICAL CHANNEL MODELING for ANALYSIS of CHANNEL PARAMETERS

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Abstract: The condition of the propagation environment is essential in the design and execution of any transmission medium. As a result, mathematical modeling of transport routes has been a focus of study for centuries. Geometrical channel modeling, as demonstrated by researchers and theorists, is best suited for mobile-to-mobile (M2M) communication settings. Several hollow cylindrical geometrical systematic collections have been thoroughly studied in this research. According to the literature, an elliptical modeling technique could more centralize national the transmission channel. Furthermore, the influence of different channel coefficients across multiple-in-multiple-out (MIMO) resonators has been illustrated utilizing geometrical models. Moreover, the velocity of a mobile station (MS) inside the M2M presenter has still not been assessed among the MIMO resonators. For 5G communications networks, a study of several mobile station (MS) variables would be given.

Keywords— M2M, MIMO, MS, Geometrical modeling, Transmission, 5G, Communication

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last few generations, there seems to be a need for transmitting massive data in real time from one with one or one to many communication nodes. As a result, offering high speed data communication lines is a basic demand of every customer in all mobile apps. Growing data rates throughout the face of restricted resources has compelled academics and thinkers to optimize the effectiveness of existing bandwidth. Furthermore, newly emerging M2M and fixed-to-mobile (F2M) communication applications are information and quality-of-service demanding (QoS). To offer actual information, sound, multimedia, and internet service providers to phone users as well as mass flow cars on roads, racecourses, and so on, to reduce the risk of disasters as well as provide QoS communication lines [1]. Mobile money service and rapidly flowing automobiles are typically found in rayleigh fading locations, and rapid development of customers in such virtualized cloud zones has a considerable detrimental influence on wireless available bandwidth [2]. As seen in Figure 1, MIMO includes various antenna arrays at both sides of the communication connection. In combination with the Harmonic dispersion, the multipath elements in these kind of transmission settings lead the transmitted power to diminish deeply. Communication connections using single-input-single-output (SISO) antenna configurations struggle heavily from aging elements, reducing operational capabilities [3]. As a result, traditional SISO antenna configurations might fail to offer the required bandwidth connections with improved QoS in F2M or M2M communication situations [4]. In such multipath settings, though, MIMO is the strongest contender for reducing the influence of aging [5]. Furthermore, MIMO antenna systems have lately been acknowledged as means of supplying high speeds in dispersing situations [6]. MIMO transmission methods apply use of spectral situations in a positive way by offering multiple antennas, which ensures a staggering rise in bandwidth [6] – [10]. Such astounding MIMO capability is possible if the program does have a strong knowledge of the different spatial features of the wireless network (H) [8].

Figure 1. MIMO communication system

Wireless dispersion networks were simulated in the literature using diverse methods to predict network characteristics. Experimental, sequential, mechanistic, and geometry-based stochastic channel modeling (GBSCM) techniques have been used by investigators and thinkers to describe the wireless transmission network [11] – [14].

II. REGULAR SHAPE GEOMETRY-BASED STOCHASTIC CHANNEL MODELS (RSGSCM)

The geometry-based stochastic channel model (GSCM) method relies on a similar structure such as circular, elliptical, cylindrical, or ellipsoidal geometries. The dispersing items in the application scenario are situated inside the geometry, and the probability distribution is defined stochastically. The GSCM technique is a hybrid of deterministic and stochastic channel modeling techniques [15].

A. Stochastic Channel Models

The stochastic channel modeling technique is based on the probability density functions (PDFs) of transmission system parameters. The precision is determined by the Patterns of angle-of-arrival/angle-of-departure (AoA/AoD), time-of-arrival/departure (ToA/D), Doppler shift, latency, hypothalamus responses, and so on. The stochastic channel simulation technique provides some advance knowledge on the statistical behavior of the wirelessly application scenario and is therefore an experimental way to tuning the performance of a stochastic wireless communication network [16]. This network modeling technique may be divided into two categories: non geometrical stochastic models (NGSMs) and GBSCM [17] – [18].

B. Non-geometrical Stochastic Channel Models (NGSM)

To construct the Summaries of channel state information in the NGSM method, no topology is used. Nevertheless, relevant symptoms such as biostatic position and AoA, AoD, and other such necessary features are defined stochastically. The benefit of NGSMs is that its essential parts little knowledge about the wireless potential field; nevertheless, they have the least power.

C. Geometrical Stochastic Channel Models (GSCM)

The GSCM technique is a hybrid of stochastic and deterministic channel estimation methods. The design of the propagation medium is represented with such a consistent geometric property in this channel estimation. The dispersing items' locations are arbitrarily dispersed in a hollow cylindrical geometry. The probability density function of channel parameters (like, AoA, AoD, ToA etc.,) are obtained with the help of fundamental laws of signal propagations [19] – [20]. Based on predefined stochastic distribution of scatterers locations GBSCMs are derived with the help of fundamental laws of diffraction, reflection, shadowing and scattering of electromagnetic waves [21]. Customers in telecommunication dispersion settings are usually located in the urban or residential regions. These regions can be associated with such a simple rectangular form such as circular, elliptical, or other form based on the arrangement of that location. In the research, researchers have proposed that geometrical channel modelling is the best technique for modelling mobile channels of communication. Furthermore, movable dispersion pathways become non-stationary. Consequently, the premise of semi dispersion situations is used to represent these dissemination social opportunities [22]. GBSCM, on the other hand, which founded on certain acceptable assumptions and is not as precise as actual channel estimation. The GBSCM findings may be confirmed by measuring voter records, allowing geometrical channel estimation that will be used to forecast attainable capacity of a digital network, and therefore to build and evaluate large networks. Furthermore, by modifying the set of parameters, which are theoretically measurable, the GBSCM method may be utilized for varied dispersion circumstances [23] – [25]. Furthermore, in non-stationary situations, the mobility of reflecting items, transmitters, or terminals may be represented using the GBSCM method [26]. As a result, many researchers and thinkers for F2M [27] – [31] and M2M [32] – [41] telecommunication settings have acknowledged the educational benefits of the GBSCM over alternate method modelling techniques in the research.

III. EXISTING GEOMETRICAL CHANNEL MODELS

Akki and Haber pioneered the geometrical channel estimation method for M2M communication connections in 1986. The suggested approach is relevant to M2M communication settings in cities and suburbs [32]. Figures 2 and 3 show the physical and geometric characteristics of the design. The researchers designed a PDF of the obtained dynamic network spectrum.

Patz ny et al. in [34], [42] expanded on Akki and Haber's study by presuming the scatterers are spread evenly like circles across the MS's, with the MS's positioned in the middle of the bands.

Figure 2. A physical environment of M2M channel

Figure 3. Geometrical layout of M2M channel

Furthermore, they have anticipated that while both transmitting MSs contain numerous antenna array components. Taking various considerations into account, they examined the suggested geometrical model, illustrated in Figure 4, for capability.

Figure 4. The 2-ring geometrical model for MIMO M2M propagation channel

Patzold et al.'s work has already been expanded by incorporating a multi-bounce two ring foundation MIMO M2M transmission scheme, as shown in Figure 5, and showing the Doppler power spectral density. The researchers of [43], [44] questioned the idea that limitless scatterers are distributed precisely and evenly at the edges of circles. The study recommends that scatterers be positioned at various dispersion ranges from the base of the tower, which they call the two-rose-ring design. The suggested designer's modeling approach is shown in Figure 6, and the writers have developed different mathematical expressions of transmission channel state information using the recommended geometry.

Figure 5. 2-ring based multi-bounce model for MIMO M2M propagation channel

Figure 6. 1-bounce and 2-bounce components in the 2-erose-ring model

Chelli et al. [45] – [46], [41] expanded the idea of isotropic surroundings of dipoles in earlier suggested models by adopting a SISO communications network. The study analyzed that dispersing items, such as a circular format and a round band, may be placed across the MSs in a non-isotropic way, and the proposed system is illustrated in Figure 7. Additionally, for collaborative transmission schemes, circular-based network models were developed. As illustrated in Figure 8, the triple mouths in the suggested model [36] are fitted with numerous antennas and are encircled by dipoles that are uniformly dispersed around the perimeter of rings. Talha et al. developed a variable formulation between MIMO antenna array components.

Figure 7. SISO antenna based M2M channel model

In the previously mentioned 2D geometrical modulation schemes, wavelet dispersion was only examined along the azimuth plane. These communication possibilities are feasible in flat urban and suburban regions devoid of tall buildings, hills, forests, and so on. These locations are dominated by quick railway lines, superhighways, and motorways. Doppler affects a vehicle wireless customer on these routes, causing information quality to decrease unexpectedly. Since the design is so varied, the suggested round performance models cannot offer significant results for those regions; nevertheless, the elliptical form is ideal for highways where rapidly moving mobile users must interact often while traveling. Strips are usually longer and thinner in dimension, thus the major axis can represent height and the secondary axis can represent dimension of the roadways. Considering the similarities, authors have found channel estimation for SISO and MIMO F2M and M2M transmission settings. The geometrical three-ring scattering model for a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ MIMO M2M channel with local scatterers on rings around the source MS, the mobile relay and the destination MS is illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Cooperative network

IV. ELLIPTICAL BASED GEOMETRICAL STOCHASTIC CHANNEL MODELS

In 1998, Ertel et al. [3] created a fresh age of geometrical data transmission centered on the elliptical form. The suggested model is about an F2M communication network in which the base station (BS) and MS are placed only at ellipsi of the ellipse and the transmission terminals are outfitted with SISO antenna structures. The scatterers zone surrounding the BS and MS is treated as both an elliptical area in Figure 9. Different shading characteristics have been established while adopting the control system of [28].

Figure 9. Elliptical scatterers density geometry

The research of Ertel et al. in [28] was improved in 2008 by Noor et al. in [12] by considering the Gaussian distribution of wavelength around MS and BS, which are positioned at the extremities of the ellipse. The researcher computed the PDF of AoA as viewed through BS, and the control system is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. SISO antenna based F2M channel model

The researchers of [47] have expanded the described earlier F2M channel estimation. Baltzis et al. presented a paradigm for M2M interaction based on two-ellipse geometry. The designers of such simulations assumed that MSs are placed in the middle of each dispersion ellipse, with scatterers spread like some kind of circle across the MS. Likewise, the public accommodations empty elliptical bouncing areas accompanied by a dispersion strip surrounding MSs in his improved version [47] of the transmission channel. The suggested model predictions are shown in Figure 11 below, and with the assistance of various constraints, the researchers have developed PDFs of AoA.

Figure 11. SISO antenna based M2M channel model

MIMO M2M cellular networks are a challenging and appropriate choice for large organizational decisions. In the research, such modes of communication have been simulated utilizing elliptical shape, as in [34], [48]. The BSs are thought to be placed there at ellipse's cores, whereas evenly scatterers are thought to be situated at the focuses of both ellipses. Antennas components have been developed using system models such as those shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Geometric elliptical scattering model for MIMO M2M channel

The existing methods in [34], [48] are relevant if the MSs are available on a particular road or alleys. Furthermore, because the BSs are located on two separate roads, as is common in our everyday lives, the results discussed in [34], [48] will be ineffective. Considering this, Wani et al. presented an elliptical-based transmission scheme in [40] in which number of nodes is considered to be situated in the cores of the ellipses. An unlimited number of dipoles are positioned at the edges of the ellipses that surround the MS's. Both extremities of the communications network have a reduced numerous antenna array.

V. GAP ANALYSIS

A significant amount of study has been conducted in the field of channel estimation of M2M and F2M communications networks. The geometrical channel modelling methodology is regarded as the best way for modelling the wireless channel. The following empirical findings are discovered during the study poll released are as follows:

- Elliptical geometry is the best form for modelling limited width roads and valleys.
- MIMO is among the most promising possibilities for enabling large storage knowledge in M2M or F2M communications networks.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The relevant actions are being taken in the proposed study to close the gap in research indicated in the following points:

- An elliptical-based geometrical network approach is formulated at first.
- Mathematical concepts are considered.
- A discussion of the simulated outcomes is held.

As a result, the suggested geometrical framework in Figure 13 could provide an ability of the system for modeling M2M communication pathways. Mobile subscribers are positioned in the cores of the elliptically arranged dispersion elements that compose the MSs in this selected framework.

Figure 13. Geometric elliptical shape based scattering model for MIMO M2M channel

On both ends of the communications network, reduced antenna structures are installed. Furthermore, only nearby scatterers are believed to be dispersion route players. Additionally, the velocity, location, and size of the propagation medium are distinct for both mobile users. The suggested geometry is used to create numerical methods for the network's different properties. These statements are implemented in Matlab, and the outcomes are explained. The diffraction pattern in the frequency band is added by movement of the emitter, recipient, or nearby items, as shown in Figure 14. In an M2M communication situation, velocity is the most significant metric.

Figure 14. Frequency shift in mobile communication scenario

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A user is in the vicinity of the first BS, which has a specific frequency at which data is transmitted. The data is transmitted via an elliptical geometric channel with a variable boundary frequency. When a user is close to an antenna, it quickly adopts the frequency. The frequency of data indicates the rate at which the receiver receives the transmitted data. The velocity of a wave is the rate at which it transports data. The frequency and speed of data transmission by users are represented by velocity, location, and distance which is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Frequency of data transmission signal

It is critical to have accurate and realistic MIMO channel models for the design and performance evaluation of MIMO wireless communication systems [1]. Channel models that account for temporal, spatial, and frequency correlation properties are especially important for the development of wideband wireless communication systems that use MIMO technologies, such as MIMO orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) systems.

Such models of space-time-frequency MIMO channels have been investigated in [40]. All the bandwidth is represented in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Bandwidth of data transmission signal

In high-speed mobile communications, Doppler frequency shift degrades wireless communication system performance. To eliminate the side effects of doppler frequency shift and improve performance, estimation of doppler frequency shift is required. There are now several schemes for estimating the doppler frequency shift, such as estimators based on vehicle speed estimation to get the maximum doppler frequency shift and estimators based on channel phase statistics [41]. The signal speed estimation shows the user's distance from the channel boundary. As the frequency rises, so does the velocity of user signals. As a result, the number of data cycles carried per second increases, and more data travels through this. The frequency difference has an effect on the bandwidth, which will change for multiple inputs and outputs and is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Effect of frequency on bandwidth

The results show in Figure 18 depicts the speed difference due to location changes: some users are at the elliptical boundary area, which has a similar speed but also a risk of data destruction because it will adopt the frequency channel pattern over time. Users who are close to the antenna are in the middle of the elliptical channel and use the accurate speed of that channel. There will be fewer opportunities for data correlation. The high number of frequency cycles indicates fast data transfer between receiver and sender; it also changes the bandwidth with little effect. The author represents speed velocity as frequency cycles per second. As the user moves away from the center, the data transfer speed slows, whereas the user close to the center has a high speed. The range of the antenna will be increased to improve efficiency, and every user at the boundary will have an appropriate velocity.

When the user receives a low frequency, it will use the nearest strong frequency pattern of a neighboring elliptical channel. If the user travels from one station to another, when the user arrives at the next station, the user will quickly adopt its frequency and speed. It will not receive slow speed, but it will detect the speed of the signals from the nearest MS.

Figure 18. Frequency and bandwidth of MIMO channel signals for multiple inputs and outputs

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a 2D elliptical-based geometrical scattering channel model proposed in Wani (2017) [41] for MIMO M2M communication environments is reviewed, and brief derivations of mathematical expressions for the correlation functions are also presented. MSs are assumed to be located at the center of each ellipse in their proposed model, whereas scattering objects are uniformly distributed around the MSs and bound within elliptical-shaped scattering regions.

Using the proposed model, they provided an expression for the joint correlation function, which is equal to the product of the transmit and receive correlation functions. For the sake of simplicity and similarity, several plots have been presented to analyze the correlation functions among the transmit antenna elements of the M2M MIMO communication link of simplicity and similarity, several plots have been presented to analyze the correlation functions among the transmit antenna elements of the M2M MIMO communication link. The obtained plots show that the correlation among antenna elements is affected by various parameters of the wireless propagation channel.

The proposed channel is elliptical in shape, and by adjusting certain parameters of its system model and positioning MSs between the elliptical regions, each user signal will have the same velocity speed when using an accurate frequency pattern.

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